

The Healing Power of Nature in William Shakespeare's Pastoral Comedy *As You Like It*

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Abstract: *The research article analyses the power of nature to reform ties between the natural world and human relations in William Shakespeare's pastoral comedy As You Like It. Thorough study of this play a major factor comes out on surface that the Forest of Arden plays a pivotal function not just as a setting of the play but as an unforeseen force that brings in substantial transformation in the understanding of a character and amends human relationships. The research traces out the important role in healing breaking social rules, revealing true selves, encouraging deep thought and creating real love. Focusing on the theory of ecocriticism and the value of nature in Renaissance literature, this study reveals how the depiction of pastoral world creates a godly sphere in which characters give up the human made social limitations and realize their true identity. The difference between court and forest works as a major platform which enables Shakespeare to explore the themes of nature against artificial world, reality against performance and corruption against renewal. This paper discusses that As You Like It demonstrates a refined ecological understanding that refers to contemporary ecological psychology by proposing that wellbeing of human psychology and social symphony are linked together with the natural world.*

Keywords: Forest of Arden, Nature, Healing, Ecocriticism, Renaissance Ecology

Introduction:

William Shakespeare's comedy *As You Like It* presents one of his most intense explorations of the mutual relationship among human world and the natural world. The major shifting of play from the immoral court to the healing Arden's natural surrounding establishes a parallel which helps Shakespeare to examine how natural world amends human point of view, personal identity and kinships. Besides serving as a setting or metaphorical device, the Forest of Arden serves as an essential healing factor that accelerates significant changes in the growth of characters and their relationships. This paper analyses the multidimensional representations of nature healing capacity throughout the play. It focuses especially on how the natural environment nurtures the realization of self and valid human relations. This paper discovers commonness in Shakespeare's use of nature as a healing force and studies their dramatic and philosophical significances by keeping in view the basic scholarship in Shakespearean ecocriticism and the ecological approaches to Renaissance literature.

This paper has undergone an interdisciplinary approach that mingles detailed textual analysis with theoretical models taken from ecocriticism, Renaissance studies and performance theory. Initial study focuses on the text of *As You Like It*, with special attention to scenes describing the initial encounter of the characters with forest, their adjustment with the natural world and the healing process they go through during their stay in the serene ecology of Arden. Secondary sources consist of analyses of Renaissance pastoral cultures and contemporary ecocritical outlook, thus bringing together a balance perspective that places this play within its historical context alongside acknowledging its existing relevance to modern ecocriticism.

Main Argument:

The Forest of Arden in *As You Like It* plays a role of a healing space between different situations of an individual where social norms are debarred and healing experience takes place. This

healing experience is inspired from the term ‘Communitas’, which according to the anthropologist Victor Turner is a phase in which preexisting differences between characters temporary vanish and a new type of community and identity takes place. The change of setting from king’s court to forest signifies the beginning of this healing experience. William Shakespeare lays down a clear difference between these two spaces- on one hand the court of Duke Frederick is replete with treacherous, pushy and hypocrites, on another hand the natural setting of Arden foster the quality of honesty, empathy and genuineness. Duke senior feels this difference after his arrival to the serene world of Arden, he admits this difference when he says,

“Hath not old custom made this life more sweet
Than that of painted pomp? Are not these woods
More free from peril than the envious court?” (Shakespeare 22)

This process of healing in the natural environment disrupts preexisting social power structure. In the Forest of Arden, Duke Senior and his acolytes constitute a temporary brotherhood community and Duke refers to his people, “my co-mates and brothers in exile” (Shakespeare 22).

The healing qualities of forest reach to temporal experience. The characters in the wilderness of Arden live ‘forest time’- a life that is out of worldly businesses. Jaques explains this totally different temporal experience in his famous speech, seven ages of man:

All the world’s a stage,
And all the men and women merely players;
They have their exits and their entrances,
And one man in his time plays many parts,
His acts being seven ages... (Shakespeare 38)

He places forest dwellers within a circular conception of time. This temporal transformation enables characters to reject their normal life and reestablish their identities and mutual relationships.

Shakespeare's portrayal of the natural environment of Arden as a healing space is more than what medieval and Renaissance conventions call "green world". The untainted setting of Arden is different from absolute pastoral setting, it also contains dangerous side with "the icy fang/ And churlish chiding of the winter's wind" (Shakespeare 22) and the fear of wild animals. This blending shows Shakespeare's deep understanding of nature as both nurturing as well as challenging space, it provides a complex setting that fortifies the healing or transformative power of nature similar to a mother who nurtures a child with both love and often mild castigation. The transformative power of the natural setting of Arden creates a suitable condition for human transformation by provisionally suspending the limits of the ascribed identities of court. C.L. Barber rightly observes that Shakespeare's natural world enables characters to "recover or discover themselves" (Barber 8). It does so by eliminating the characters from the artificiality of human world and bringing them in affinity to the natural setting of the Forest of Arden.

The raw nature of Arden plays a crucial role in disclosing real selves that were either hidden or suppressed within the artificiality of court life. This disclosure of true selves takes place in various modes, for example physical loss that tatters hypocrisy and exposure to natural world that requires genuine responses. The exposure to the natural world healed Orlando the most. In the court life, his innocence and lack of understanding makes him a prey to his brother's conspiracy, but in the forest his virtuous qualities flourish. Orlando's true nature is observed by Adam when he utters: "O, what a world is this, when what is comely / Envenoms him that bears it!"(Shakespeare 25), his speech suggests that his real self could not be duly appreciated within an immoral court life. After his arrival to the natural world of Arden, his qualities shine and he becomes a compassionate good leader and a creative poet. Likewise, Rosalind in the disguise of Ganymede ironically expresses her true self in the natural forest life. Her male identity, in disguise, liberates her to cross the confining gender expectations of court life. In the forest, she enjoys a life that was quite

impossible in court- “I’ll have no worse a name than Jove’s own page, / And therefore look you call me Ganymede” (Shakespeare 21). Her identity that she experienced in the forest life enables her to become more direct, witty and emotionally intelligent, the qualities which were earlier curbed in the artificial life of court.

The most explicit transformation was observed in Duke Senior after his lively experience in the natural world of Arden. The way he acknowledges the teachings of mother-nature shows how exposure to the natural world facilitates real self-knowledge:

“And this our life, exempt from public haunt,
Finds tongues in trees, books in the running brooks,
Sermons in stones, and good in everything” (Shakespeare 22).

The way Shakespeare reveals identity of his characters through nature reflects the humanism culture of Renaissance that distinguishes appearance and reality, and between social performance and authentic being. There is no performance pressure in forest, which is quite contrary to court life, and hence it allows authentic identity to emerge. Modern psychological concept of “ecological self” (Naes 1995) was already available in the characters of Shakespeare who could experience their true identity through exposure to the natural world, Arne Naes explains that human identity comes into existence partly through connection with natural environment. Shakespeare, through the transformation of his characters, intends to say that one cannot properly know themselves without experiencing the transformative nature of the natural world. This concept continues to exist in the modern environmental psychology.

The Forest of Arden is not just a forest, it provides an aura which stimulates characters’ psyche. Characters experience extraordinary philosophical growth after their exposure to the natural world, which they had never experienced in the court life. After exposure to the natural world the characters throughout the play delve in deep contemplation about time, justice, morality and human

nature. The major philosophical voice is reflected in the character of Jaques, his melancholic character and insightful observations are triggered by forest experiences. His philosophical insight lightens up after his encounter with the wounded deer which shows nature's cruelty and human hypocrisy. The natural environment of forest gives philosophical wisdom to Duke Senior too. He says, "This is no flattery. These are counselors / That feelingly persuade me what I am" (Shakespeare 22) - in this utterance he compares the authenticity of natural life to court life that manifests the intellectual clarity provided by the natural world is quite rare to see in the corrupt court life. The counselors in the court were flatterers while in the forest they were harsh but real, which helps Duke Senior in true understanding and moral development.

The major attention of Orlando was on romantic love, but his interaction with the natural world Arden fills him with philosophical ideas. Initially he threatens the company of Duke Senior "Forbear, and eat no more!" (Shakespeare 36), but later a sense of humanity arises within him and he asserts,

"I thought all things had been savage here,
And therefore put I on the countenance
Of stern commandment" (Shakespeare 37).

This change in the attitude of Orlando from a stern to a compassionate being demonstrates the healing capacity of nature to stimulate moral development. Nature as a philosophical catalyst depicted by Shakespeare is drawn from Renaissance humanist traditions that observed the natural environment as a source of wisdom outside academic teachings. According to Robert Watson Shakespeare's pastoral world often functions as unconventional academics in which characters learn from first-hand experience, which is contrary to institutional learning. The learning earned through real life experience plays better role in transformation in comparison to formal education, as aforementioned in Orlando's moral development. This philosophical learning earned in the serenity of Arden finally crosses the boundary of forest as well, the

characters transfer these learnings to the court society. The Restoration of Duke Senior assures governance inspired by the forest environment which suggests that the philosophical influence of nature transcends individual enlightenment to a positive social change. Modern environmental philosophy also asserts that understanding of the natural world promotes sustainable and fair social systems.

The healing power of nature in *As You Like It* is in its most significant form is seen in authentic human connections, especially romantic love. Shakespeare consistently portrays the natural world of forest as important to the growth of genuine relationships that was impossible in the court society. The romantic relationship between Orlando and Rosalind prospers after their arrival to the Forest of Arden. Although their initial love begins at court but their relationship flourishes in the forest environment. The forest environment provided Rosalind freedom to be disguised as Ganymede and offered her opportunity for liberated communication that was not possible in the usual courtship ritual. Her communication with Orlando justifies the forest as an essential space for the development of their relationship where she says, “you shall tell me where in the forest you live. Will you go?” (Shakespeare 53) Their courtship ritual, in which Orlando woos Ganymede, displays a fabricated romantic convention generated in the forest environment. Rosalind’s dialogue, “I would cure you, if you would but call me / Rosalind, and come every day to my cote, and woo me.” (Shakespeare 53), suggests that natural environment of forest fosters a lesson of relationship which is impossible in the constrained life of court society. In a similar way minor characters also understand romantic relationships in the forest environment. Silvius and Phebe, and Touchstone and Audrey get their loving partners in the Forest of Arden. The natural setting of Arden plays a pivotal role in their love life, in the forest environment they learn to express their feelings of love to their loving ones. The simultaneous development of love in these characters demonstrates nature’s healing power to nurture true human love beyond rigid social codes of court society. Shakespeare’s depiction of nature as

important factor to nourish pure love demonstrates Renaissance pastoral traditions. This portrayal of nature as a facilitator of authentic love reflects contemporary studies in environmental psychology, which suggests that natural environment strengthens human bonds through better empathy and attention. In the modern context Richard Louv observes that natural setting often functions as “relationship catalysts” by eliminating all distractions that hinders genuine love.

After their life-changing experience in the natural environment of the Forest of Arden most of the characters return to the court society, but the transformation in their thought, feelings and understanding remains with them. Shakespeare’s portrayal of this return implies that the transformative effect of nature lasts beyond immediate forest experience and it has the potential to rebuild court society. Duke senior’s restoration ensures better governance inspired from wisdom gained from forest environment. He would not have experienced such transformation in his governance abilities without his exile to the Forest of Arden. Orlando’s return to court as a confident nobleman from earlier an ignorant disinherited young boy also signifies the healing power of nature to transform a timid person into a valiant one, from an arrogant to a compassionate one. Jaques decision to stay with Duke Frederick in seclusion exemplifies everlasting influence of the impact of life lived in the natural environment of forest. After experiencing genuine philosophical voice in serene natural environment he decides to stay with his altered self: “Out of these convertites / There is much matter to be heard and learned” (Shakespeare 90). His decision implies that good changes, similar to healing, should be carried throughout the life.

Shakespeare’s portrayal of return of the characters from forest to court life is not as simple as it seems to be. The composite portrayal of resuming to court life after a short escape to the natural setting of Arden highlights Shakespeare’s ecological wisdom. Shakespeare does not intend to present forest as a temporary escape in *As You Like It* but as a healing process that

undergoes during interaction with the natural environment of forest and even after return to the court life. This understanding reflects contemporary environmental psychology of how exposure to the natural environment still influences human development and social functioning even if direct contact to the natural environment ends.

Conclusion:

In the modern world where people are getting disconnected to the natural environment and human activities are leading to environmental crisis, the healing power of nature as represented by William Shakespeare plays an essential role. The healing power of nature in *As You Like It* reflects “attention restoration theory” (Kaplan 1995), which according to environmental psychologists is the understanding that interaction with natural environment treats mental fatigue and restore cognitive ability. For instance, characters like Orlando and Rosalind were mentally strained in the artificial court society but they experience intellectual and creative boom in the Forest of Arden. Similarly, Shakespeare’s portrayal of the forest as facilitator of real identity anticipates modern concept of “ecological self” (Naess 1995), which means the understanding that the development of human identity takes place partly through relationship with natural environment. The modern world is confronting numerous ecological challenges and Shakespeare’s narration of natural world as a healing agent in *As You Like It* depicts human nature harmony and ecological wisdom. His imagination of development of human with harmonious connection with nature provides hope for better human life and warning for such people who are continuously getting disconnected from nature’s healing power.

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